

Integrating spatially detailed micro-environmental attributes to a routable transport network for active travel modelling: A pilot study in Greater Manchester

S.M. Labib^{*1,2}, Irena Itova¹, Corin Staves¹, Belén Zapata-Diomedí³, Alan Both³, Lucy Gunn³, Haneen Khreis¹, Ali Abbas¹, Aruna Sivakumar⁴, Jenna Panter¹, Billie Giles-Corti³, and James Woodcock¹

¹ MRC Epidemiology Unit, University of Cambridge, Cambridge, UK

²Department of Human Geography and Spatial Planning, Utrecht University, Netherlands

³Centre for Urban Research, RMIT University, Australia

⁴Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, Imperial College London, UK

January 17, 2022

Summary

Prior studies show that the Built Environment (BE) can influence route and mode choice, increasing the uptake of active modes and reducing car dominance. One of the main challenges in establishing such relationships between the BE and travel behaviour is the unavailability of micro-scale BE data. This study presents a methodology for harmonising and joining multi-source spatial datasets to the unit level of the street segment (link). We observed significant link-level variations of the environmental characteristics, which would have been missed with more traditional area-level approaches. Thus more detailed information of specific street segments can assist travel demand modelling.

KEYWORDS: Built environment, OpenStreetMap, Data harmonisation, Transport network, Active travel

1. Introduction

Traditional research on urban environmental exposures often underestimates the health impacts of the outdoor environment because they focus on exposures around the home or work environment at the neighbourhood scale (Orellana and Guerrero, 2019; Kim et al., 2014; Liu et al., 2020). Studies focused on residential locations or neighbourhoods ignore exposures experienced by individuals away from home (Kwan, 2009), and they do not consider how the physical environment along travel corridors influences an individual's active travel behaviour. For example, Lu (2021) demonstrated that area-based estimates of PM_{2.5} personal exposures were underestimated by 13%, and this exposure bias significantly increased (up to 61%) for people exhibiting high mobility levels (> 32 km).

Previous studies on transport and environmental health usually focus on multiple meso-scale area-based measurements of environmental exposures, such as the built and natural environment. These studies mostly have used the concepts of 3Ds (density, diversity, and design) or 5Ds (3D plus “destination accessibility” and “distance to transit”) developed by Cervero et al. (2009). While the “D” variables are widely utilised in understanding travel-related behaviour at meso-scale, they are vulnerable to variations in the size and scale of areal measurement units and the modifiable areal unit problem (MAUP, Openshaw, 1981). The MAUP can cause the associations between exposures and health outcomes to vary based on the scale and size of the aggregation unit (Labib et al., 2020). Furthermore, aggregation of variables at the meso-scale unit results in uniformed values for the variables, which may not reflect the variation of conditions across the area (Strominger et al., 2016). For example, a high-quality cycling route is only useful if it connects users to destinations. Therefore, such infrastructure may not be equally accessible to all users living within the neighbourhood. These issues with meso-scale measurements of environmental exposure can lead to erroneous assessments of environmental

* s.m.labib@uu.nl

exposure, individual experience, and overall modelled relationships.

To reduce errors in environmental exposure assessments, a better representative individual travel experience and improved micro-environmental health indicators are essential. The granular information allows to understand the level of people’s exposure to different environments and if and how these exposures modify users’ behaviour towards mode choice and route choice (Ettema et al., 2010; Liu et al., 2020). Our study examines whether including microenvironment attributes along the transport network reduces exposures misclassification and improves modelling outcomes. The results of this study would also allow developing informed urban planning and policy decisions regarding what microenvironmental characteristics should be promoted in urban design to increase active travel in cities.

2. Methods and Materials

2.1. Data Sources

In order to create a routable transport network with the micro-environmental attributes, we harmonised spatial data from multiple sources, including OpenStreetMap, Ordnance Survey, CycleStreets, Satellite images, and modelled the network spatial dataset (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Multi-source spatial data for varying network and micro-environmental indicators and major methodological steps.

2.2 Methodological steps

2.2.1 Download and clean OSM data

We used OpenStreetMap (OSM) to construct the base road network of the study area. We downloaded the OSM dataset with the “highway” tag to create the road network. We utilised code from the Cycling Infrastructure Prioritisation Toolkit (Lovell and Parkin, 2018) to remove any unnecessary tags in the cleaning process.

2.2.2 Create a routable road network

We used the cleaned OSM line dataset to create a routable road network by converting line strings to a spatial graph object consisting of edges (links) and nodes. This process included adding pseudo nodes, finding the largest connected cluster of links, and providing unique link and node IDs.

2.2.3 Adding micro-scale environmental variables

We added several physical, traffic, built, and natural environmental indicators to the network links created in the previous step. These micro-scale indicators were grouped under two broad categories of factors that can influence route and mode choice for active travel: safety-related indicators; and attractiveness indicators (Mertens et al., 2014; Liu et al., 2020).

For safety-related indicators, we joined additional road infrastructure information such as width and traffic calming features from the Ordnance Survey. Further, we added traffic volume information on major and minor roads based on the Department of Transport's counts and the model developed by Morley and Gulliver (2016). From Transport for Greater Manchester (TfGM), we obtained data on the observed 85th percentile speed, presence of cycling infrastructure, crossing, signal, and street lights. From CycleStreets, we collected data on the presence of modal filters and the quietness index for each link (Figure 1). To join the attributes from the input datasets onto the routable network, we sampled points along the lines. Thereafter, we spatially joined these points to the network links using distance threshold (identified iteratively using Hausdorff distance) to transfer the input attributes onto the routable network. The slope of each link was estimated using the Digital Terrain Model (5 m resolution).

To reflect the *attractiveness* of network links for cycling and walking, we added information about the surrounding greenness (e.g., normalised difference vegetation index- NDVI, eye-level visibility). To create the NDVI, we used Sentinel-2 satellite data and applied the viewshed-based greenness visibility model developed by Labib et al. (2021). Additionally, we used the points of interest (POIs) database from the Ordnance Survey to identify POIs which may positively or negatively contribute in using a specific link, based on its attractiveness for cycling or walking. Positive POIs include the presence of cafes, shops, and negative POIs include places that generate heavy traffic such as construction services or create an ambient for non-scenic walking, such as large parking lots or office parks. We used spatial clustering algorithms such as KNN, and DBscan to identify clusters of POIs in proximity to each link. Shannon and Simpson indices were used to quantify the diversity and dominance of POIs for each link. Finally, we joined the number of crimes reported at each link using Greater Manchester's police dataset.

The overall workflow and spatial operations can be reproduced for any other city-regions in the UK. We created a GitHub Organization and multiple repositories for this project, <https://github.com/jibeproject>. The majority of the code was developed in R-programming language using multiple packages, including osmdata, sf, sfnetworks, tidygraph, igraph, ngeo, slope, qgisprocess, terra, dbscan, vegan, tidyverse, and GVI (Brinkmann and Labib, 2021).

3. Results and Discussion

The outcome is a routable transport network (graph: links and nodes) with 40 key road and micro-environmental attributes of each link. Figure 2 illustrates a few selected physical and built attributes on the links in central Manchester. From Figure 2, it is clear that creating detailed attribute information of each link allows exploring spatial variability of different attributes of the network at a fine scale. For instance, the highest speed is observed on the Mancunian way (Fig 2A), a motorway road. We also observed that the majority of the streets have sidewalks (Fig 2B), but only a few have cycling infrastructure (Fig 2C), which is common for the UK. Also, the majority of the roads have a width between 8-12 m (Fig 2D).

Figure 2 Selected safety-related physical and built link attributes for Manchester city centre area.

Figure 3 Selected attractiveness-related attributes for Manchester city centre area.

Additionally, we identified spatial patterns of attractiveness attributes for each link (Figure 3). As expected, Figure 3B indicates that eye-level greenness in the city centre is very low (less than 10% on most links), while the links in this area have a high diversity of POIs (Figure 3A). The contrasting patterns of attractiveness-related attributes indicate that links could be simultaneously attractive and unattractive, depending on the micro-scale environmental characteristics surrounding them.

In summary, the spatial patterns of attractiveness and safety-related attributes are crucial in understanding the overall experience of journeys on the network and reducing exposure misclassification, particularly for active travel. These micro-environmental attributes contribute to the composite perceived impedance of different routes for different modes, especially cycling (Orellana

and Guerrero, 2019). The combined indicators will be validated using empirical evidence (such as Strava cycling data) and active travel demand modelling. Further research will address several limitations of this study, such as the inaccuracy of the variables' values stemming from the methodological limitations in the spatial joining process, which on some network links attaches attribute values in their absence. Another limitation is the incompleteness of the input datasets with missing values due to variance in the resolution of the dataset. The imputation methods used to reduce missing data are also presented. Additionally, several input data has limitations regarding generalisation. For example, the police data aggregate the reported crime on the centroid of each street, which does not reflect the actual location of the crime.

4. Acknowledgements

This study is part of Joining Impact models of transport with spatial measures of the Built Environment (JIBE) project. JIBE was supported by the UKRI-NHMRC Built Environment Prevention Research Scheme (#MR/T038578/1, APP1192788) and this funding is gratefully acknowledged. Papers using background IP or data from other projects with other funders should ensure that this is acknowledged either by citing relevant papers or as appropriate, in the acknowledgements. Sources of fellowship funding for relevant investigators on the manuscript should also be acknowledged: e.g., BGC is supported by an NHMRC Senior Principal Research Fellowship (1107672). The authors acknowledge the support of Cyclestreet (<https://www.cyclestreets.net/>) for their support in providing Quietness and modal filter data. We also recognise the contributions of the TfGM team for their support in collecting data and discussing TfGM's policies.

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Biographies

- S.M. Labib** is Assistant Professor of Data Science & Health, at Utrecht University and a visiting research associate at the Public Health Modelling Group, in the MRC Epidemiology Unit, University of Cambridge. His research interests in spatial data science, GIS and their applications in environmental epidemiology, and urban health.
- Irena Itova** is a temporary Research Associate at the Public Health Modelling Group, in the MRC Epidemiology Unit, University of Cambridge. She is a PhD candidate at the University of Westminster with a research focus on complex networks, infrastructure integration, and systems' complexity.
- Corin Staves** is a PhD Student at the MRC Epidemiology Unit, University of Cambridge. His research interests are at the intersection of transport modeling and public health modeling, with a focus on microsimulation and agent-based methods.
- Belen Zapata-Diomedí** is an RMIT University Vice-Chancellor's Research Fellow at the Center of Urban Research, RMIT University. Her research interests include modelling of health impacts related to transport behaviors and built environment interventions.
- Alan Both** is a Research Fellow at the Center of Urban Research, RMIT University. His research interests are in spatial data science, GIS, and Agent-Based Modelling of active transport behaviors.
- Lucy Gunn** is a Senior Research Fellow at the Center of Urban Research, RMIT University. Her research interests are in modeling relationships between the built environment, transport, and health in assessing built environment interventions.
- Haneen Khreis** is a Senior Research Associate, at the Public Health Modelling Group, in the MRC Epidemiology Unit, University of Cambridge. She is also an Associate Research Scientist at Texas A&M Transportation Institute where she is a technical advisor on select projects. Her research interests are in exposure assessment, especially noise and air pollution, models' validation, and advancing health impact assessment methodologies.
- Ali Abbas** is a Senior Data Scientist at the Public Health Modelling Group, in the MRC Epidemiology Unit, University of Cambridge. He is a public health modeller and is interested in developing good understandings of an environment-friendly and sustainable transport system with a positive impact on public health.
- Aruna Sivakumar** is reader in consumer demand modeling and urban systems at the Centre for Transport Studies, Imperial College London.
- Jenna Panter** is a Senior Research Associate at the Population Health Interventions group, in the MRC Epidemiology Unit, the University of Cambridge. Her research focuses on understanding the effects of environmental changes on walking and cycling, the effects on physical activity.
- Billie Giles-Corti** is an RMIT Vice-Chancellor's Professorial Research Fellow and Director of the Healthy, Liveable Cities Lab at the Center of Urban Research, RMIT University. Her research interests are in measuring relationships between the built environment and health in support of the evidence-based policy.
- James Woodcock** is a Professor of Transport and Health Modelling at MRC Epidemiology Unit, University of Cambridge. He leads the Public Health Modelling group. His research focuses on cities and health in the transition to the zero-carbon society. He is an ERC Consolidator Grant holder.